

D3.6 Innovative HPC Technologies and Benchmarking

Date: 26 June 2026

Document Identification			
Status	Final	Due Date	30/06/2026
Version	1.0	Submission Date	26/06/2026

Related WP	WP3	Document Reference	D3.6
Related Deliverable(s)	D3.4, D3.1, D5.3, D5.4, D5.6	Dissemination Level (*)	PU
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Keywords:
High Performance Computing (HPC); AMD EPYC; Turin; Zen5; Zen5c; Intel Xeon, Granite Rapids; profiling, co-design.

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Document History			
Version	Date	Change editors	Changes
0.1	12/05/2026	Lukasz Szustak (PSNC)	Initial consortium draft with table of contents, guidance notes, placeholders, and pilot contribution template.
0.2	14/05/2026	Marcin Lawenda (PSNC), Shubham Kavane (FAU)	ToC, responsibilities, and section ownership confirmed by consortium.
0.3	22/05/2026	Lukasz Szustak (PSNC)	Architecture overview
0.4	12/06/2026	Lukasz Szustak (PSNC)	Performance-Energy analysis of WRF.SFIRE
0.5	15/06/2026	Ioanna Tasou (ICCS)	LLM overview
0.6	17/06/2026	Lukasz Szustak (PSNC)	Benchmark methodology
0.7	17/06/2026	Marcin Lawenda (PSNC)	Executive Summary, Introduction
0.8	19/06/2026	Lukasz Szustak (PSNC)	WRF pilot description, conclusion, and text polishing
0.9	24/06/2026	Lukasz Szustak (PSNC)	Changes after the internal review

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0.95	26/06/2026	Shubham Kavane (FAU)	Quality assurance check
1.0	26/06/2026	Marcin Lawenda (PSNC)	Final check and improvements

Quality Control		
Role	Who (Partner short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable Leader	Lukasz Szustak (PSNC)	24/06/2026
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Figure 29. Theoretical performance comparison of serial(left) vs. parallel(right) transformer pipeline. 61

List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALU	Arithmetic Logic Unit
AMX	Advanced Matrix Extensions
AOCC	AMD Optimizing C/C++ and Fortran Compilers
CCD	Core Complex Dies
CCX	Core Complex
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSR	Compressed Sparse Row
CXL	Compute Express Link
DDR5	Double Data Rate version 5
DIMM	Dual In-Line Memory Module
DLMC	Deep Learning Matrix Collection
EC	European Commission
EMIB	multi-die interconnect bridge
GCC	GNU Compiler Collection
GIPS	Giga Instructions Per Second
GMI	Global Memory Interconnect
HCC	High Core Count
HDR	High Data Rate (HDR) InfiniBand
HDR	High Data Rate
HPC	High Performance Computing
I/O	Input/Output
IOD	I/O Die
IPC	Instructions per Cycle
ISA	Instruction Set Architecture
L1, L2, L3	Cache Level 1, 2 and 3
LLC	Low Core Count
LLM	Large Language Model

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MCM	Multi-Chip Module
MKL	Math Kernel Library
MPI	Message Passing Interface
NDR	Next Data Rate
NPS	NUMA Nodes Per Socket
NUMA	Non-Uniform Memory Access
P2P	Point Two Point
PCIe	Peripheral Component Interconnect Express
PTI	Per Thousand Instructions
QKV	Query, Key, and Value
SDDMM	Sampled Dense-Dense Matrix Multiplication
SIMD	Single Instruction Multiple Data
SMT	Simultaneous Multithreading
SNC	sub-NUMA clusters
SoC	System on a Chip
SpMM	Sparse Matrix-Matrix Multiplication
TDP	Thermal Design Power
UCC	Ultra Core Count
UPI	UltraPath Interconnect
WF	WildFire model
WP	Work Package
WRF-SFIRE	Weather Research and Forecast (WRF) - a fuel moisture parameterization (SFIRE)
XCC	Extreme Core Count
Zen	AMD multi-chip architecture
μProf	AMD profiling tool

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Executive Summary

The report outlines trends in innovative High Performance Computing architectures associated with established HPC processor manufacturers. This analysis primarily concentrates on the advanced AMD EPYC 9004 and 9005 series processors, including the novel 128-core and 192-core models based on the Zen 5 and Zen 5c microarchitectures, together with the Intel Xeon 6 (Granite Rapids) processors, and includes a discussion of the testbeds used. The Wildfires pilot serves as a foundation for evaluating these architectures. The simulation relies on the WRF-SFIRE model, a coupled fire-atmosphere model based on the Weather Research and Forecast (WRF) model, in which an empirical fire spread model combined with a fuel moisture parameterisation is dynamically coupled with local meteorology. Following the description of the use case, the methodology for benchmarking the processors is outlined, covering the benchmark procedure, resource binding and allocation, and the profiling and energy measurement tools employed. The performance and energy evaluation focuses on the WRF-SFIRE code executed on AMD EPYC platforms representing the Genoa, Genoa-X, and Turin generations, as well as on Intel Granite Rapids processors, using configurations from one to four compute nodes. A central element of this work is the assessment of hybrid MPI+OpenMP execution, where the number of OpenMP threads per MPI rank is varied while the total core count is kept constant. The results reveal that the runtime minimum is consistently located at four OpenMP threads per rank across all evaluated AMD platforms and node counts, confirming that the optimal balance is largely independent of system scale. The cross-platform comparison examines runtime, average node power demand, and total energy consumption, while the profiling and MPI analysis explains the observed behaviour through cache efficiency, memory throughput, and communication characteristics, including the influence of domain decomposition on halo exchange volume. Finally, the report explores the performance, scalability, and parallel scheduling of sparse transformer architectures for large language model inference on CPU-based HPC systems. By replacing dense kernels with Sparse Matrix-Matrix Multiplication and Sampled Dense-Dense Matrix Multiplication, sparsification reduces both memory overhead and computational cost. The analysis demonstrates the theoretical potential of scheduling independent matrix operations concurrently across the transformer pipeline, while identifying the practical limitations imposed by resource contention, thread affinity behaviour in vendor libraries, and static partitioning constraints.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The deliverable D3.6 is a continuation of the D3.5 [1] report. Its primary goal is to provide information on new hardware and software technologies that can be applied to simulation calculations to potentially improve the functionality and performance of HiDALGO2 codes. Testing new architectures is related to the recognition of newly introduced hardware solutions for the HiDALGO2 project pilot applications. In this deliverable, the Wildfires use case is used to evaluate the latest AMD EPYC processors and the Intel Xeon 6 (Granite Rapids) processors, with particular emphasis on hybrid MPI+OpenMP execution and on the joint analysis of performance and energy consumption. The deliverable also examines the performance, scalability, and parallel scheduling of sparse transformer architectures for large language model inference on CPU-based HPC systems, a workload of growing relevance to environmental computing.

1.2 Relation to other project work

As already mentioned, this deliverable D3.6 is a continuation of the work presented in D3.4 [2] and D3.5 [1], expanding the hardware base with the 128-core and 192-core AMD EPYC 9005 models based on the Zen 5 and Zen 5c microarchitectures and adding the Intel Xeon 6 (Granite Rapids) processor. In addition, the work extends the analysis of the Wildfires use case towards hybrid MPI+OpenMP execution and the joint study of performance and energy consumption. Therefore, the current tests concern the WRF-SFIRE application from the Wildfires pilot. The description of the use cases themselves can be found in the dedicated WP5 deliverables, and their scalability tests on EuroHPC JU machines in the WP3 reports. Both this and the other mentioned reports are subject to extensions as part of ongoing further research.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is organised into seven sections focusing on specific testing topics. In addition to this section (introduction), it contains:

Section 2 presents trends in innovative HPC architectures that represent traditional HPC processor vendors. This study focuses on the AMD EPYC 9004 and 9005 series processors, including the 128-core and 192-core models based on the Zen 5 and Zen 5c microarchitectures, and the Intel Xeon 6 (Granite Rapids) processor, together with a description of the test platforms.

Section 3 presents the HiDALGO2 Wildfires pilot for the aspects required by these tests and delineates the benchmarking methodology, covering the benchmark

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procedure, the strategy for resource binding and allocation, and the profiling and energy measurement tools used in the study.

Section 4 elaborates the experimental results and the performance-energy analysis obtained for WRF-SFIRE. It evaluates hybrid MPI+OpenMP configurations, compares performance and energy across the AMD EPYC and Intel platforms, and presents the profiling and MPI communication analysis.

Section 5 discusses the performance analysis of sparse large language model inference on CPU-based HPC systems, examining the scalability of sparse kernels and the parallel scheduling of the transformer pipeline.

Section 6 summarises the work elaborated in the above sections, highlighting the most significant achievements.

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2 Architectures overview

This section presents trends in innovative HPC architectures developed by traditional HPC processor vendors. The investigation focuses on AMD processors, continuing the work previously conducted in D3.4 and D3.5. It covers the state-of-the-art AMD EPYC 9005 processors, including the novel 128-core and 192-core models based on the Zen 5 and Zen 5c architectures, respectively. In addition, this section outlines the Intel Xeon 6 processors, including a high-core-count 128-core model equipped with a large cache memory.

2.1 AMD EPYC 9004 family

The 4th generation AMD EPYC 9004 family comprises high-performance server processors based on the Zen 4 and Zen 4c architectures. Introduced in 2022, these processors provide a substantial performance improvement over previous generations, such as Rome and Milan, by offering higher core counts, increased clock frequencies, and support for DDR5 memory and PCIe 5.0 interfaces. The family includes multiple processor variants designed to address diverse workload demands, making them well suited for high-performance computing (HPC) and AI environments. It is important to note that Deliverable D3.4 [2] offers an in-depth overview of the AMD EPYC 9004 processor family. This document distinguishes three CPU types: Genoa, Genoa-X, and Bergamo. In particular, it includes detailed evaluations of the 64-core and 96-core Genoa processors, as well as the 96-core Genoa-X models, which are also employed in the current study to assess performance gains achieved by the latest CPU generations.

2.2 AMD EPYC 9005 family

The latest AMD EPYC 9005 processor family, referred to the Zen 5 and Zen 5c microarchitectures, represents a significant evolution of the 4th generation EPYC 9004 series. While the previous generation introduced the Zen 4 and Zen 4c cores through the Genoa, Genoa-X, and Bergamo processor variants, the new AMD EPYC Turin (9005 series) platform further extends AMD’s HPC capabilities by increasing core density, improving energy efficiency, and delivering higher overall performance. The AMD EPYC Turin can therefore be considered a direct continuation and advancement of the successful Genoa (9004 series) platform.

It is important to underline that Deliverable D3.5 [1] provides an in-depth overview of the AMD EPYC 9005 processor family, focusing primarily on the 96-core Zen 5-based solutions. In contrast, the current document presents results from the investigation of higher-core-count Zen 5 and Zen 5c processors, including the latest 128-core and 192-core CPU configurations.

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2.3 AMD Zen 5 and Zen 5c architectures

The standard Zen 5 architecture is designed for workloads that require high per-core performance combined with strong computational throughput. These processors are manufactured using an advanced 4 nm process technology and support configurations of up to 128 cores and 256 threads per socket. The architecture primarily targets HPC, AI, and enterprise applications that benefit from higher clock frequencies, improved IPC, and enhanced floating-point performance.

In contrast, the Zen 5c architecture is optimized for extreme core density and energy-efficient massively parallel computing. Built using a 3 nm manufacturing process, Zen 5c processors enable configurations with up to 192 cores and 384 threads per socket, currently representing one of the highest core-count x86 server solutions available. The Turin Dense product line extends the design philosophy previously introduced with the Bergamo processors in the EPYC 9004 generation, focusing on throughput-oriented workloads and highly scalable HPC environments.

Unlike the earlier EPYC 9004 family, which offered the Genoa-X variants equipped with AMD 3D V-Cache technology for cache-intensive HPC workloads, the EPYC 9005 generation does not currently include a direct Zen 5-based successor to the Genoa-X processors.

Both Zen 5 and Zen 5c share the same underlying microarchitectural design and ISA compatibility, delivering substantial improvements in Instructions per Cycle (IPC), execution efficiency, and operating frequencies over previous Zen generations. Each compute core integrates a 32 KB 8-way associative L1 instruction cache together with an enlarged 48 KB 12-way associative L1 data cache, representing a 1.5x increase in L1 data cache capacity compared to earlier designs. In addition, every core contains a private unified 1 MB L2 cache dedicated to both instructions and data, while all cache levels utilize a 64-byte cache line size.

The AMD EPYC Turin processors also introduce significant advancements in vector and floating-point processing performance. Both Zen 5 and Zen 5c cores support native full-width AVX-512 execution using dedicated 512-bit data paths and registers, substantially increasing SIMD throughput for HPC and AI workloads. These improvements are enabled through wider execution engines, expanded floating-point pipelines, larger scheduling structures, and optimized single-cycle AVX-512 data handling. Furthermore, all cores support simultaneous multithreading (SMT), allowing two hardware threads to execute concurrently on a single physical core and improving overall resource utilization and parallel execution efficiency.

The AMD EPYC 9005 family preserves the proven chiplet-based multi-chip module (MCM) architecture introduced in earlier EPYC generations. This scalable design integrates a high number of compute cores, memory controllers, and I/O components within a unified System-on-Chip (SoC) platform. The processor package is composed of multiple Core Complex Dies (CCDs), each incorporating a single Core Complex (CCX) based on the Zen 5 or Zen 5c microarchitecture. All CCDs communicate through

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a centralized high-performance I/O die interconnected via the AMD Infinity Fabric, enabling low-latency and high-bandwidth communication between compute, memory, and I/O subsystems.

The standard Turin-based processors integrate up to eight standard Zen 5 cores within a single Core Complex (CCX), sharing a 32 MB L3 cache, which corresponds to 4 MB of L3 cache per core. Each CCX is implemented on a dedicated Core Complex Die (CCD). A complete processor package may contain up to 16 CCDs, enabling configurations with up to 128 cores and a total of 512 MB shared L3 cache. Figure 1 illustrates the AMD EPYC 9005 system on chip block diagram consists of 128 cores grouped in 16 CCDs with classic Zen 5 core and a central IOD.

In contrast, the dense Turin processors accommodate sixteen Zen 5c cores grouped within a single CCX sharing the same 32 MB L3 cache, corresponding to 2 MB of L3 cache per core. This design enables the development of high-density processors featuring up to 192 cores distributed across 12 CCDs, providing a total of 384 MB of L3 cache. Such a high core density is achieved at the expense of reduced L3 cache capacity available per core compared to the standard Zen 5 configurations. Figure 2 illustrates the AMD EPYC 9005 system on chip block diagram consists of 192 cores grouped in 12 CCDs with classic Zen 5 core and a central IOD.

The central I/O Die (IOD) of the AMD EPYC 9005 processors integrates memory controllers, PCIe 5.0 interfaces, GMI links, and Infinity Fabric interconnects. The platform supports twelve DDR5 memory channels with up to 24 DIMMs per socket, enabling a maximum memory capacity of 9 TB and memory bandwidth reaching 576 GB/s per socket with DDR5-6000 memory.

Similar to previous EPYC generations, the Turin platform employs a Non-Uniform Memory Access (NUMA) architecture, where memory access latency depends on the proximity between compute cores and memory controllers. To optimize performance, the processors support multiple NUMA Nodes Per Socket (NPS) configurations, including NPS1, NPS2, and NPS4, allowing flexible partitioning of memory and CCD resources depending on workload requirements.

The Turin-based processors also provide up to 128 PCIe 5.0 lanes in single-socket systems. In dual-socket configurations, part of the PCIe connectivity is reassigned for socket-to-socket communication using AMD Infinity Fabric, resulting in 64 PCIe lanes per socket while maintaining 128 lanes for the complete two-socket platform.

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Figure 1. AMD EPYC Turin 128-core model with 16 CCX and a central IOD based on Zen 5 architecture.

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Figure 2. AMD EPYC Turin 192-core model with 12 CCX and a central IOD based on Zen 5c architecture.

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2.4 Intel Xeon 6 (Granite Rapids)

The Intel Xeon 6 family based on the Granite Rapids architecture represents Intel latest generation of high-performance server processors targeting HPC, AI, cloud, and enterprise workloads. Granite Rapids continues Intel’s transition toward disaggregated multi-tile processor designs, significantly increasing scalability, core counts, cache capacity, and memory bandwidth compared to previous Xeon generations such as Sapphire Rapids. Similar to the tiled organization introduced in Sapphire Rapids (see Deliverable D3.5 description about Intel Xeon Max [1]), the Granite Rapids architecture integrates multiple compute tiles interconnected through Intel’s high-speed on-package interconnect technologies, enabling efficient communication between cores, cache, memory controllers, and I/O subsystems.

Granite Rapids introduces two processor classes based on different core types: Performance-cores (P-cores) and Efficient-cores (E-cores). The P-core variants target workloads requiring high single-thread and floating-point performance, including HPC simulations and AI applications. The flagship Intel Xeon 6980P processor integrates up to 128 P-cores with Intel Hyper-Threading enabled, supporting up to 256 concurrent hardware threads. In contrast, the E-core variants are optimized for higher core density and improved energy efficiency, reaching up to 144 cores in the Sierra Forest Xeon 6 processors. This division resembles AMD’s approach of separating standard Zen 5 and dense Zen 5c processor variants.

The Granite Rapids P-core processors are based on Intel’s Redwood Cove microarchitecture and support advanced instruction set extensions such as AVX-512 and Intel Advanced Matrix Extensions (AMX), enabling accelerated vectorized computations and AI-oriented matrix operations. The architecture provides large shared L3 caches, enhanced DDR5 memory subsystems, PCIe 5.0 connectivity, and Compute Express Link (CXL) support for accelerator and memory expansion technologies.

The Xeon 6 processors adopt a modular tiled organization composed of compute and I/O tiles connected through Intel packaging technologies such as EMIB and high-speed die-to-die interconnect fabrics. The compute tiles integrate processor cores together with portions of the cache hierarchy, whereas the I/O dies provide PCIe, CXL, and UPI connectivity. The compute dies are manufactured using the Intel 3 process technology, while the I/O dies are fabricated using Intel 7 technology. Figure 3 illustrates the Intel Xeon 6 system block diagram consists of 128 P-cores grouped in 3 tiles.

Similar to previous Xeon generations, Granite Rapids utilizes a mesh interconnect topology to connect cores, cache slices, memory controllers, and I/O resources within the processor package. The mesh-based organization improves data movement efficiency across the processor and allows the architecture to scale toward very high core counts while maintaining balanced memory access characteristics. The Granite Rapids architecture is available in several configurations that differ in the number of compute tiles, enabled cores, and cache capacity.

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Figure 3. Intel Xeon 6 based on 128-core UCC model with 3 compute and 2 IO tiles.

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Depending on the processor configuration, Xeon 6 with p-core-based processors are available as 1-tile, 2-tile, or 3-tile designs, supporting configurations ranging from compact 16-core LLC (Low Core Count) models through 48-core HCC (High Core Count), and 86-core XCC (Extreme Core Count) variants up to the 128-core UCC configuration (Ultra Core Count). HCC and XCC variants integrate additional compute tiles and larger cache hierarchies to improve scalability for HPC and highly parallel workloads. The UCC variants represent fully enabled configurations with the maximum number of compute tiles and cores supported by the architecture.

The Xeon 6 processors support both single-socket and dual-socket configurations and feature up to 12 DDR5 memory channels operating at speeds reaching 6400 MT/s. Furthermore, the platform supports up to 96 PCIe 5.0 lanes and six UPI 2.0 links, enabling high-bandwidth communication between processors, accelerators, storage, and networking devices.

2.5 Target platforms

This section presents the infrastructure used for the benchmarks described in the following sections. The study includes a series of state-of-the-art AMD EPYC processors based on different architectures, including: (i) four compute nodes equipped with dual 96-core Genoa-X CPUs, (ii) four compute nodes equipped with dual 96-core Genoa CPUs, (iii) four compute nodes equipped with dual 96-core Turin CPUs, (iv) two compute nodes equipped with dual 128-core Turin CPUs, and (v) four compute nodes equipped with dual 192-core Turin Dense CPUs. The investigation is further complemented by experiments performed on a server equipped with dual 128-core Intel Xeon CPUs. Access to the underlying infrastructures is provided by Intel and AMD companies.

Most AMD-based platforms are interconnected using high-performance NVIDIA Mellanox InfiniBand networks. The Genoa-X and 96-core Turin platforms utilize ConnectX-6 adapters operating at HDR 200 Gb/s, while the Genoa, 128-core Turin, and 192-core Turin Dense platforms employ newer ConnectX-7 adapters with NDR 400 Gb/s connectivity. The Intel Granite Rapids platform is evaluated as a standalone dual-socket server without InfiniBand interconnect usage in the performed tests. A brief specification of the evaluated systems is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Target platforms specification.

Platform	Nodes	CPU	Cores per node	Codename	Memory per node	Infiniband
AMD	4	9654	2x 96	Genoa	768 GB DDR5-4800	ConnectX-7 NDR 400 Gb/s

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AMD	4	9684X	2x 96	Genoa-X	768 GB DDR5-4800	ConnectX-6 HDR 200 Gb/s
AMD	4	9655	2x 96	Turin	768 GB DDR5-6000	ConnectX-6 HDR 200 Gb/s
AMD	2	9755	2x 128	Turin	768 GB DDR5-5600	ConnectX-7 NDR 400 Gb/s
AMD	4	9965	2x 192	Turin Dense	1536 GB DDR5-6400	ConnectX-7 NDR 400 Gb/s
Intel	1	6980P	2x128	Granite Rapids	1536 GB DDR5-6400	NA

Table 2 shows a brief summary of the parameters offered by processors [3] [4]. The target processors feature different numbers of cores and are clocked by the base frequency clocks listed in Table 2. The CPU designs of all the platforms feature the out-of-order execution model and support the frequency boost technology, where the maximum turbo frequency depends on the type and intensity of workload and the number of utilized cores. The SMT is turned off for all the systems.

Table 2. A single CPU specification.

Vendor	AMD	AMD	AMD	AMD	AMD	Intel
CPU Type	9654	9684X	9655	9755	9965	6980P
Codename	Genoa	Genoa-X	Turin	Turin	Turin	Granite Rapids
Architecture	Zen4	Zen4	Zen5	Zen5	Zen5c	Redwood Cove P-core
Cores	96	96	96	128	192	128
Clock [GHz] (Turbo)	2.4 (3.55)	2.55 (3.42)	2.6 (4.1)	2.7 (4.1)	2.25 (3.35)	2.0 (3.2)
L1i/L1d [KB]	32/32	32/32	32/48	32/48	32/48	48/64
L2 per core [MB]	1	1	1	1	1	2
CCX	8-core	8-core	8-core	8-core	16-core	NA
L3 CCD [MB]	32	96	32	32	32	NA
#CCD in CPU	12	12	12	16	12	NA
Total L3 [MB]	384	1152	384	512	384	504

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L3 per core [MB]	4	12	4	4	2	3.94
Memory Type	12-channel DDR5 up to 4800 MT/s	12-channel DDR5 up to 4800 MT/s	12-channel DDR5 up to 6400 MT/s			

The AMD EPYC 9654 processor, based on the Zen 4 architecture and codenamed Genoa, integrates 96 cores organized across 12 CCDs, where each CCD contains an 8-core CCX configuration with 32 MB of shared L3 cache. As a result, the processor provides a total of 384 MB of L3 cache, corresponding to approximately 4 MB of L3 cache per core. Each core additionally integrates 32 KB instruction and 32 KB data L1 caches together with 1 MB of private L2 cache. The processor operates at a base frequency of 2.4 GHz with boost frequencies reaching up to 3.55 GHz. The memory subsystem consists of a 12-channel DDR5 controller supporting memory speeds up to 4800 MT/s. In the evaluated configuration, the platform is organized into four NUMA domains (NPS4).

The AMD EPYC 9684X processor extends the Genoa architecture by employing AMD 3D V-Cache technology in the Genoa-X family. Similarly to the EPYC 9654, the processor integrates 96 Zen 4 cores distributed across 12 CCDs using an 8-core CCX organization. However, the additional vertically stacked cache significantly increases the L3 capacity to 96 MB per CCD and 1152 MB in total, corresponding to approximately 12 MB of L3 cache per core. Such a large cache capacity is particularly beneficial for memory-sensitive HPC workloads, including finite element methods, computational fluid dynamics, sparse matrix operations, and graph-oriented applications. The processor operates at a base frequency of 2.55 GHz with boost frequencies reaching up to 3.42 GHz. Similar to the standard Genoa platform, the processor utilizes a 12-channel DDR5-4800 memory subsystem and the evaluated systems are configured using four NUMA domains (NPS4).

The AMD EPYC 9655 processor belongs to the Turin generation and introduces the newer Zen 5 microarchitecture while maintaining the 96-core configuration. The processor integrates 12 CCDs with 8-core CCX organization and provides 384 MB of total L3 cache. Compared to the previous Zen 4 generation, Zen 5 introduces architectural improvements targeting instruction throughput, branch prediction, frontend efficiency, and floating-point execution capabilities. In addition, the processor increases supported DDR5 memory frequency up to 6400 MT/s, improving achievable memory bandwidth. Each core integrates 32 KB instruction and 48 KB data L1 caches together with 1 MB of private L2 cache. The processor operates at a base frequency of 2.6 GHz with boost frequencies reaching up to 4.1 GHz. Similar to the Genoa-based systems, the evaluated Turin platforms are configured using four NUMA domains (NPS4).

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The AMD EPYC 9755 processor represents a higher-core-count Zen 5 Turin configuration integrating 128 cores distributed across 16 CCDs. Each CCD utilizes the same 8-core CCX organization with 32 MB of shared L3 cache, resulting in a total L3 capacity of 512 MB and approximately 4 MB of L3 cache per core. The processor operates at a base frequency of 2.7 GHz with boost frequencies reaching up to 4.1 GHz. Similar to the EPYC 9655, the processor supports 12-channel DDR5 memory operating at speeds up to 6400 MT/s. The combination of high core count, large aggregate cache capacity, and increased memory bandwidth makes the processor suitable for highly parallel HPC and AI workloads requiring strong scalability across many execution threads. The evaluated systems are configured using four NUMA domains (NPS4).

The AMD EPYC 9965 processor belongs to the Turin Dense family and is based on the Zen 5c microarchitecture optimized for maximum core density and energy efficiency. The processor integrates 192 cores organized across 12 CCDs, where each CCD contains a denser 16-core CCX configuration. Despite maintaining 32 MB of L3 cache per CCD, the significantly increased number of cores reduces the available L3 cache per core to approximately 2 MB. The processor operates at a base frequency of 2.25 GHz with boost frequencies reaching up to 3.35 GHz. Similar to other Turin processors, the EPYC 9965 supports 12-channel DDR5 memory operating at up to 6400 MT/s. The Zen 5c architecture focuses on maximizing throughput-oriented workloads and parallel scalability while maintaining high computational density within a dual-socket server platform. The evaluated systems are configured using four NUMA domains (NPS4).

Among the Granite Rapids processors, the Intel Xeon 6980P represents the flagship P-core model and one of Intel’s highest-performing server processors currently available. The processor is based on the Redwood Cove P-core microarchitecture and integrates 128 Performance-cores with Intel Hyper-Threading enabled, allowing execution of up to 256 concurrent hardware threads. In contrast to AMD’s CCD-based organization, Granite Rapids utilizes a tiled architecture interconnected through Intel mesh fabric. The processor provides more than 500 MB of shared L3 cache distributed across the compute tiles, corresponding to approximately 3.9 MB of L3 cache per core. Each core integrates 48 KB instruction and 64 KB data L1 caches together with 2 MB of private L2 cache. The processor operates at a base frequency of 2.0 GHz with turbo frequencies reaching up to 3.2 GHz. The memory subsystem consists of a 12-channel DDR5 controller supporting memory speeds up to 6400 MT/s. In the evaluated configuration, the system is organized into three NUMA domains (SNC3).

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3 Benchmarking methodology

This section describes the benchmarking methodology employed in this work. The evaluation is conducted on testbeds equipped with AMD EPYC 9004/9005 and Intel Xeon 6 processors using the Wildfires pilot application as a representative HPC workload. The methodology covers performance profiling, MPI communication analysis, energy measurements, and the assessment of MPI rank mapping and resource allocation strategies. These analyses provide the basis for evaluating application scalability, communication patterns, and energy efficiency on modern processor architectures.

3.1 Benchmark procedure and the Wildfire pilot overview

In this stage of the HiDALGO2 project, as a continuation of the D3.5 [1] report, the main goal of the tackled activity is to provide information on new hardware and software technologies that can be applied to simulation calculations to potentially improve the functionality and performance of the models used in HiDALGO2. This report focuses on the Wildfires use case that is one of the pilots of HiDALGO2. The primary objective of the Wildfire pilot (WF) is to explore the use of HPC resources for operational and preventive planning purposes in wildfire management. The simulation of wildfires at the landscape scale has been explored using the WRF–SFIRE model (version 4.4), which is a coupled fire-atmosphere model based on the Weather Research and Forecast (WRF) model. It uses the WRF model to simulate meteorology, while an empirical fire spread model combined with a fuel moisture parameterization (SFIRE) is dynamically coupled with local meteorology. The layout of the simulation domain is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. WRF-SFIRE domains with grid resolution of 9 km, 3 km, 1 km and 200 m for domains D01, D02, D03 and D04 respectively [1].

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The simulation of wildfires and related atmospheric phenomena requires spatial resolutions on the order of a few hundred meters for the atmospheric mesh and a few tens of meters for the wildfire mesh. Indeed, dividing the volumetric calculation domain into regions (tiles) allows the process to be distributed across an equivalent number of cores in HPC installations, thus reducing the final computation time and enabling simulations across large portions of territory. More information about WRF pilot is presented in [5].

As shown in Deliverable D3.5 [1], the benchmark is based on the complete WRF-SFIRE simulation workflow, which consists of the sequential execution of five applications provided within the benchmark test case: geogrid, ungrib, metgrid, real, and wrf.sfire. Preliminary benchmarking results indicate that the wrf.sfire execution phase refers to the most computationally demanding component of the workflow. Since the runtime of wrf.sfire accounts for the vast majority of the total simulation time, the analyses presented in the following sections of D3.6 focus primarily on this application. In our experiments, all programs are compiled with GCC and linked against MPI pre-installed by platform vendors (OpenMPI v.4.1.8). The GCC compiler (v.13.3) is used. All the systems operate with SMT disabled and turbo boost enabled.

In order to guarantee the reliability of benchmark results, the measurements of execution time are repeated several times, and the median value of measurements is used finally. We note here that all measurements reported in the subsequent sections show the execution time for five runs. To simplify the measuring process, we developed a set of wrapping Python and Bash scripts that help us manage the entire benchmarking process across all platforms.

3.2 WRF-SFIRE execution model

The benchmark configuration of the WRF.SFIRE code employs four nested computational domains with resolutions of 9 km, 3 km, 1 km, and 200 m, respectively. The parent-to-child grid refinement ratios are equal to 3, 3, and 5, while the corresponding parent time-step ratios follow the same values. Consequently, the outermost domain (D01) advances with a time step of 54 s, whereas D02, D03, and D04 use time steps of 18 s, 6 s, and 1.2 s, respectively.

As a result, the nested configuration introduces a hierarchical execution pattern. During a single time step of D01, domain D02 performs three integration steps. Similarly, each D02 step triggers three D03 steps, and each D03 step performs five D04 steps. As a result, one D01 time step corresponds to 9 D03 steps and 45 D04 steps. Over the entire one-hour simulation period, D01 executes 67 time steps, D02 performs 201 steps, D03 performs 603 steps, and D04 performs 3015 steps. Consequently, the vast majority of computational work is concentrated in the finest-resolution domains, particularly in D04 where the wildfire model is activated. The nested WRF-SFIRE domains differ in spatial resolution and time-step size, leading to different computational intensities. Hierarchy of the four nested WRF-SFIRE domains is illustrated in Figure 5. Increasing spatial resolution requires proportionally smaller time

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steps, causing the innermost domain (D04) to execute 45-time steps for every single time step performed by D01, as previously mentioned.

Figure 5. Spatial nesting structure and time-step ratios of the four computational domains.

Parallel execution relies on a hybrid MPI+OpenMP strategy (see Figure 6). Each computational domain is partitioned among MPI processes using domain decomposition, while the work assigned to each MPI rank is further parallelized across multiple OpenMP threads. During the numerical integration phase, neighboring MPI ranks exchange halo data using point-to-point (P2P) communications (Figure 6b). These exchanges occur repeatedly within the dynamics and physics kernels and represent the dominant source of MPI communication overhead. Within each MPI process, OpenMP threads execute computational loops concurrently and share access to the local subdomain data. Additional communication is required at domain nesting boundaries, where child domains receive boundary conditions from their parent domains and periodically return feedback information to coarser domains.

Collective MPI operations are performed less frequently and are primarily associated with global synchronization, reductions, and distributed I/O operations (Figure 6c). In addition, updates between nested domains (e.g., feedback from a finer domain such as d04 to its parent domain d03, or interpolation of boundary conditions from parent to child domains) are generally implemented through data exchanges between the MPI processes responsible for the overlapping regions rather than through global collective operations. The communication pattern therefore consists of a large number of short-range point-to-point exchanges, including halo updates and nested-domain interactions, combined with a smaller number of collective synchronization events.

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Figure 6. Hierarchical domain decomposition (a) and communication mechanisms, including point-to-point (b) and collective communication schemes (c), in the WRF-SFIRE simulation.

As a result, neighbouring MPI ranks exchange halo data through point-to-point communications within each domain, while additional data transfers occur between parent and child domains to provide boundary conditions and feedback updates.

The simulation also performs periodic output operations. Atmospheric and fire-state variables are written to disk at regular intervals defined by the model configuration. In the considered benchmark, output is generated every 180 minutes for D01 and every 60 minutes for the nested domains. These cyclic I/O operations introduce additional

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synchronization and data movement overhead, which becomes increasingly visible at larger process counts and therefore constitutes an important aspect of the overall performance analysis.

The parallel decomposition of each computational domain is determined using the automatic decomposition mechanism provided by WRF. For a given number of MPI processes, the decomposition algorithm attempts to create subdomains with dimensions as close to square as possible in order to minimize the surface-to-volume ratio of each partition. This approach reduces the relative size of halo regions and consequently limits the amount of point-to-point communication required between neighboring MPI ranks. Although perfectly square subdomains are not always achievable due to domain dimensions and process-count constraints, the automatic decomposition aims to maintain a balanced workload distribution while minimizing communication overhead across the computational grid.

To limit the overall benchmarking cost while preserving representative application behaviour, all experiments were restricted to a single 60-minute simulation period. This approach assumes that the computational workload, communication patterns, and resource utilization remain statistically stable throughout the simulation and that the measured performance characteristics are representative of longer production runs. Consequently, the obtained runtime, communication, and energy measurements can be used to assess the relative performance of the investigated hardware platforms and parallel execution configurations without requiring a full-length wildfire simulation.

3.3 Resource binding and allocation

The execution of WRF-SFIRE was controlled using an explicit MPI rank and OpenMP thread mapping strategy. In all experiments, the application was launched with the following command pattern:

```
mpirun --bind-to core --map-by \
ppr:$MPI_PER_NODE:node:pe=$OMP_TH \
--report-bindings -np $MPI_NP wrf.exe
```

This configuration binds each MPI rank to a dedicated set of CPU cores and assigns OMP_TH processing elements to every rank. The parameters in the command pattern `ppr:$MPI_PER_NODE:node:pe=$OMP_TH` mapping places a specified number of MPI processes on each compute node while reserving the required number of cores for the OpenMP threads associated with each rank. As a result, different hybrid MPI+OpenMP configurations can be evaluated while maintaining explicit control over process and thread placement.

The MPI process placement was complemented by explicit OpenMP affinity settings. The `OMP_PROC_BIND=close` option keeps OpenMP threads close to their parent MPI rank, while `OMP_PLACES=cores` ensures that individual threads are pinned to dedicated physical cores. Together, these settings minimize thread migration, improve cache utilization, and enhance NUMA locality. Such placement is particularly important

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for WRF-SFIRE, where each MPI rank operates on a local subdomain and repeatedly exchanges halo data with neighbouring ranks.

The adopted mapping and affinity strategy provides a consistent execution environment across all investigated processor architectures and node counts, allowing the performance differences observed in later sections to be attributed primarily to hardware characteristics, communication behaviour, and scalability properties.

Figure 7 illustrates an example of 12x16 domain decomposition distributed across four compute nodes. Each node contains two CPU sockets, and MPI ranks are assigned to subdomains while preserving locality within the available processor resources.

Figure 7. Example of MPI rank placement for a 12 × 16 domain decomposition on a four-node dual-socket cluster.

3.4 Profiling tools

The profiling study primarily focuses on AMD-based platforms, including processors from the AMD EPYC 9004 (Zen 4) and AMD EPYC 9005 (Zen 5) families. This emphasis was motivated by the availability of detailed hardware-performance monitoring capabilities provided by AMD μ Prof, as well as the broader access to AMD-based testbeds throughout the project. In contrast, access to Intel Xeon 6 systems was more limited, restricting the scope of low-level microarchitectural investigations on that platform.

3.4.1 Hardware-performance profiling

To investigate the interaction between WRF-SFIRE and the underlying processor architecture, detailed hardware-performance profiling is conducted using the AMD μ Prof toolkit. AMD μ Prof [6] is a comprehensive performance analysis suite designed

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To collect the profile data for a single application run and a given platform, we use AMDuProfPcm tool with properly selected groups of metrics, for example:

```
AMDuProfPcm -a -C -A system,core -m avx_imix,cache_miss,dc,\
fp,ipc,l1,l2,l3,pipeline_util -- ./wrf.exe
```

The AMDuProfPcm utility collects hardware performance-counter data during application execution and reports both system-level and core-level metrics. The `-a` option enables monitoring of all processor cores, while `-C` activates CSV output generation for post-processing and analysis. The `-A system,core` option requests the collection of metrics at both the overall system level and the individual core level, enabling the investigation of application behaviour across the entire processor hierarchy.

The profiling configuration focuses on several groups of microarchitectural metrics. The `avx_imix` group characterizes the instruction mix and utilization of vector execution units, providing insights into the degree of SIMD exploitation. The `cache_miss`, `l1`, `l2`, and `l3` groups capture cache utilization and miss behaviour across different levels of the memory hierarchy. The `dc` group reports data-cache-related activity, while the `fp` group provides information about floating-point instruction execution. The `ipc` metrics quantify instruction throughput in terms of instructions executed per cycle, whereas the `pipeline_util` group characterizes the efficiency of processor pipeline utilization and helps identify potential front-end or back-end bottlenecks.

Together, these metrics provide a comprehensive view of application behaviour, enabling the identification of computational, memory, and communication bottlenecks. The collected data are subsequently used to compare the execution characteristics of WRF-SFIRE across the investigated AMD Zen 4 and Zen 5 processor architectures.

3.4.2 Power and energy measurements

In addition to performance profiling, the benchmarking methodology includes power and energy measurements in order to evaluate the energy efficiency of different processor architectures and hybrid MPI+OpenMP configurations. The measurements were performed using the AMD μ Prof Command Line Interface (AMDuProfCLI), which provides access to processor-level power monitoring capabilities available on AMD EPYC platforms. Power measurements are collected using the AMD μ Prof timechart facility configured to monitor socket-level power consumption:

```
AMDuProfCLI timechart --event socket,power --system-wide --interval 1000
```

The `socket,power` event records the power consumption of all processor sockets within a node, while the `--system-wide` option enables monitoring of the entire system rather than individual processes. Measurements are sampled every 1000 ms, providing a one-second temporal resolution throughout the execution of the benchmark. Separate power traces were collected for each compute node participating in the simulation.

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```

16 PROFILED COUNTERS
17 COUNTER ID,NAME,CATEGORY,UNIT,DESCRIPTION
18 1152.,socket0-package-power,Power,W,Socket0-Average Package Power reported in Watts.
19 1154.,socket1-package-power,Power,W,Socket1-Average Package Power reported in Watts.
20
21 PROFILE RECORDS
22 RecordId,TimeStamp,socket0-package-power,socket1-package-power
23 1,21:31:3:447, 208.93, 215.49
24 2,21:31:4:447, 251.44, 250.87
25 3,21:31:5:447, 409.02, 409.04
26 4,21:31:6:447, 402.59, 402.46
27 5,21:31:7:447, 401.73, 401.68
28 6,21:31:8:447, 405.83, 406.03
29 7,21:31:9:447, 409.02, 409.02
30 8,21:31:10:447, 409.43, 409.02
31 9,21:31:11:447, 409.02, 409.42
32 10,21:31:12:447, 399.22, 399.34
33 11,21:31:13:447, 409.02, 409.43
34 12,21:31:14:447, 409.02, 409.02
35 13,21:31:15:447, 409.42, 409.43
36 14,21:31:16:447, 408.72, 408.70
37 15,21:31:17:447, 409.66, 409.66
38 16,21:31:18:447, 409.04, 409.02
39 17,21:31:19:447, 409.43, 409.43
40 18,21:31:20:447, 409.01, 409.00
41 19,21:31:21:447, 409.43, 409.44
42 20,21:31:22:447, 409.09, 409.01
43 21,21:31:23:447, 401.56, 401.88
44 22,21:31:24:447, 406.59, 406.56
45 23,21:31:25:447, 409.48, 409.44
46 24,21:31:26:447, 408.97, 409.01
47 25,21:31:27:447, 409.48, 409.45
48 26,21:31:28:447, 409.02, 409.01
49 27,21:31:29:447, 409.41, 409.43
50 28,21:31:30:447, 409.02, 409.00
51 29,21:31:31:447, 409.43, 409.03
52 30,21:31:32:447, 408.91, 409.43
53 31,21:31:33:447, 409.49, 409.01
54 32,21:31:34:447, 409.06, 409.43
55 33,21:31:35:447, 409.02, 409.01
56 34,21:31:36:447, 409.43, 409.43
57 35,21:31:37:447, 409.01, 409.00
58 36,21:31:38:447, 409.43, 409.44
59 37,21:31:39:447, 409.02, 409.01
60 38,21:31:40:447, 409.42, 409.43
61 39,21:31:41:447, 409.01, 409.02
62 40,21:31:42:447, 409.43, 409.42

```

Figure 9. Example of AMDuProfCLI power analysis results.

It should be underlined that only a single MPI rank per node is launched under the control of AMDuProfCLI, while the remaining MPI ranks executed the application normally. This approach allows the power-monitoring process to capture node-level processor power consumption while avoiding multiple concurrent monitoring instances on the same node. However, this methodology requires manual mapping of MPI ranks and OpenMP threads to the available hardware resources to ensure that the monitored rank is placed appropriately and that the application execution remains consistent across all benchmark configurations.

The collected power traces were subsequently post-processed to obtain average power consumption and total energy usage of every node as a sum of two CPUs. The average power was computed as the arithmetic mean of all sampled power values recorded during application execution. The total energy consumption was calculated by integrating the measured power over the execution time.

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The proposed methodology enables a direct comparison of execution time, average power consumption, and total energy usage across different processor architectures and parallel execution configurations. Consequently, it provides a comprehensive view of both performance and energy efficiency characteristics of the WRF-SFIRE application on modern HPC platforms.

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4 Experimental results and performance-energy analysis

This section presents the performance evaluation results of the WRF-SFIRE code. The study investigates a series of AMD EPYC CPUs representing the Genoa, Genoa X, and Turin generations, together with Intel Granite Rapids processors. Experiments were conducted using configurations comprising from one to four compute nodes. Since energy and power measurements are not available for the tested Intel Xeon 6980P platform, the energy-power analysis is limited to the AMD EPYC systems.

In this section, WRF-SFIRE is analysed using the AMD μ Prof profiling tools on AMD platforms. In addition to selected system-level performance metrics, dedicated MPI profiling is employed to investigate the communication behaviour of the hybrid MPI/OpenMP implementation. The following discussion focuses on the most relevant profiling metrics for understanding the communication characteristics and scalability of the application.

4.1 Evaluation of hybrid MPI+OpenMP configurations

To evaluate the impact of the OpenMP-MPI hybrid version of the WRF-SFIRE code, the number of OpenMP threads per MPI rank is varied while keeping the total number of used CPU cores constant. The tested configurations ranged from pure MPI execution (OMP=1) to 16 OpenMP threads per rank. Figure 10 presents the runtime analysis of the WRF-SFIRE application achieved on six computing platforms using configurations with 1–16 OpenMP threads per MPI rank and 1–4 compute nodes. In addition, Figure 11 shows the performance improvement relative to the pure MPI execution setup with OMP = 1, quantifying the benefits of hybrid MPI+OpenMP execution.

As shown in Figure 11a-e, the consistent trend is observed across all evaluated AMD platforms. The consistency of the runtime curves across one-, two-, and four-node executions indicates that the optimal MPI/OpenMP balance is largely independent of the system scale. In all evaluated AMD platforms, the runtime minimum remains located at OMP=4, demonstrating that the hybrid decomposition strategy scales well with increasing node count.

Considering all tested AMD platforms, a significant runtime reduction is observed when moving from the pure MPI configuration to hybrid MPI+OpenMP execution. On the 2x96-core Genoa system, the runtime decreases from approximately 815 s for OMP=1 to 573 s for OMP=4 (a single node test), corresponding to a speedup of about 1.4x (Figure 10a and in Figure 11a). Similar improvements are observed on the 2x96-core Genoa-X platform, reducing runtime from 649 s to 494 s (Figure 10b and in Figure 11b). The same behaviour is visible on the Zen 5-based systems. For the 2x96-core Turin platform (Figure 10c and in Figure 11c), the runtime decreases from 660 s to 456 s as the OpenMP thread count increases from 1 to 4. The larger 2x128-core and 2x192-core Turin processors (Figure 10d-e and in Figure 11 d-e) exhibit comparable characteristics, with the lowest runtime consistently obtained for OMP=4. In particular, the 2x192-core Turin system achieves a reduction from approximately 831 s to 430 s

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on a single node, representing nearly a twofold improvement compared to the pure MPI execution model. Importantly, the same trend is maintained for two- and four-node executions. Although the absolute runtime decreases with increasing node count, the optimal configuration remains unchanged, with OMP=4 consistently delivering the shortest execution time across all evaluated AMD platforms. This observation indicates that the benefits of hybrid MPI+OpenMP execution are largely independent of the system scale and are primarily associated with achieving a more favourable balance between MPI communication overhead and OpenMP parallelism.

Figure 10. Impact of OpenMP threads per MPI rank on application runtime.

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Figure 11. Performance gains relative to the pure MPI configuration (OMP=1).

A similar trend is observed on the Intel Xeon 6980P platform. The runtime decreases from 673 s for OMP=1 to 536 s for OMP=4, corresponding to a speedup of approximately 1.26x (Figure 11f). Further increasing the thread count causes performance degradation, and the OMP=16 configuration becomes slower than the pure MPI execution.

Although the magnitude of the improvement is smaller than on the AMD systems, the location of the optimum remains unchanged. Increasing the number of OpenMP threads beyond four does not provide additional benefits. In most cases, OMP=8 results feature similar runtimes, while OMP ≥ 16 leads to a more noticeable performance degradation. This effect is visible across all AMD platforms and indicates

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that the reduction in MPI communication can no longer compensate for the increased synchronization costs and reduced load balance associated with larger OpenMP teams. The results suggest that reducing the number of MPI ranks provides a significant benefit for WRF-SFIRE. When OMP=4 is used, the number of MPI processes is reduced by a factor of four compared to the pure MPI configuration, leading to lower communication overhead and fewer synchronization points. At the same time, the OpenMP parallel regions remain sufficiently small to avoid excessive thread-management overhead.

Overall, the experiments indicate that the optimal balance between MPI communication and OpenMP parallelism is achieved with four OpenMP threads per MPI rank. This configuration consistently delivers the shortest execution time on all evaluated AMD EPYC and Intel Xeon platforms, regardless of processor generation or core count.

Figure 12 shows the average node power consumption of WRF-SFIRE for different numbers of OpenMP threads per MPI rank. Unlike runtime, average power generally decreases as the OpenMP thread count increases. This trend is observed across all evaluated AMD EPYC platforms and is particularly visible on the Genoa and Turin systems. For example, on the 2x96-core Genoa platform, the average node power decreases from approximately 808 W for OMP=1 to 656 W for OMP=8 and further to 610 W for OMP=16.

Similar behaviour is observed on the Genoa-X platform, where the average power is reduced from approximately 815 W to 658 W. The Zen 5 based Turin systems exhibit comparable characteristics, with the largest reductions observed on the higher core-count processors. On the 2x192-core Turin platform, the average node power decreases from approximately 978 W for OMP=1 to 823 W for OMP=16. The overall trend remains consistent across all evaluated systems and node counts.

The reduction in power consumption can be attributed to the lower number of MPI processes and the associated decrease in communication activity. As the OpenMP thread count increases, a larger fraction of execution time is spent in shared-memory parallel regions, reducing MPI-related overheads and leading to lower average power demand.

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Figure 12. Impact of OpenMP threads per MPI rank on average node power consumption.

Figure 13 presents the total energy consumption of WRF-SFIRE for different hybrid MPI+OpenMP configurations. In contrast to average power, the total energy consumption is determined by the combined effect of runtime and power demand. Across all evaluated AMD platforms, the lowest energy consumption is generally achieved for OMP=4 or OMP=8 configurations. For example, on the 2x96-core Genoa platform, the energy consumption decreases from approximately 0.16 kWh for the pure MPI configuration to approximately 0.11 kWh for OMP=4, corresponding to an energy reduction of about 30%. Similar improvements are observed on the Genoa-X and Turin systems. Furthermore, the same behaviours are maintained for one-, two-, and four-node executions, indicating that the energy benefits of hybrid execution are noticeable for all tested configurations.

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Although larger OpenMP teams continue to reduce average power consumption, the observed increase in runtime ultimately outweighs these benefits. Consequently, the OMP=16 configuration often consumes more energy than OMP=4 despite operating at lower average power levels. This observation highlights the importance of jointly considering runtime and power consumption when evaluating energy efficiency

Figure 13. Impact of OpenMP threads per MPI rank on total energy consumption.

Figure 14 illustrates the energy gain relative to the pure MPI configuration (OMP=1). The results demonstrate substantial energy savings across all evaluated platforms, with the highest gains consistently obtained for OMP=4, which also corresponds to the runtime optimum identified in the previous section. Depending on the processor architecture and node count, the energy gain achieved with OMP=4 typically ranges from approximately 1.3x to 1.8x, meaning that the application requires 30–45% less energy to complete the same workload compared to the pure MPI execution model.

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Figure 14. Energy gains relative to the pure MPI configuration (OMP=1).

In addition, Figure 14 reveals a strong correlation between performance improvement and energy savings. In general, configurations that achieve the largest runtime reductions also provide the highest energy gains. For example, on the 2x96-core Genoa platform, the performance gain increases from 1.0x for OMP=1 to approximately 1.42x for OMP=4 and 1.47x for OMP=8. At the same time, the corresponding energy gain rises from 1.0x to approximately 1.45x and 1.60x, respectively. Similar behaviour can be observed on the Genoa-X and Turin platforms, indicating that improvements in execution time directly translate into lower energy consumption. However, this relationship is no longer maintained for larger OpenMP configuration. Although OMP=16 typically operates at lower average power levels, the increase in runtime reduces both the performance and energy benefits. Consequently,

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the configurations providing the highest performance gains are also those delivering the largest energy savings, with OMP=4 consistently representing the best compromise between runtime reduction, power consumption, and overall energy efficiency across all evaluated platforms and node counts.

Overall, the results demonstrate that average power consumption, total energy consumption, and energy gain can be considered jointly when evaluating hybrid MPI+OpenMP configurations. While increasing the number of OpenMP threads generally lowers power demand, the most energy-efficient execution is achieved when both runtime and power consumption are simultaneously minimized. Across all evaluated platforms, as well as for one-, two-, and four-node executions, OMP=4 consistently provides the most favourable balance between execution time, power demand, and overall energy efficiency.

4.2 Cross-Platform Performance and Energy Comparison

The results presented in the previous section demonstrated that the hybrid MPI+OpenMP configuration employing four OpenMP threads per MPI rank consistently provides the best balance between runtime, power consumption, and overall energy efficiency across all evaluated platforms and node counts. Consequently, the OMP=4 configuration is identified as either the performance-optimal or energy-optimal setup in all cases. To enable a meaningful comparison of processor architectures, the analysis presented in this section focuses mainly on the OMP=4 configuration. The investigated systems include AMD EPYC Genoa, Genoa-X, Turin, and Turin Dense processors, together with the Intel Xeon 6980P platform.

Figure 15 compare the runtime of WRF-SFIRE application achieved on the evaluated AMD EPYC and Intel Xeon platforms using the OMP=4 configuration identified in the previous section as the most effective hybrid MPI+OpenMP setup. As shown in Figure 15, the observed performance differences between the evaluated processor generations. The 2x96-core Genoa platform represents the baseline Zen 4 architecture and delivers the longest execution times among the AMD systems. Introducing AMD 3D V-Cache technology in the 2x96-core Genoa-X platform reduces runtime by approximately 10–15%, depending on the node count. This result indicates that WRF-SFIRE benefits from the significantly larger last-level cache available in Genoa-X processors. The larger cache capacity appears to reduce memory access latency and improve data locality within the most frequently executed computational kernels.

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Figure 15. Runtime comparison across evaluated platforms when using OMP=4 configuration.

A further performance improvement is observed when moving from the Zen 4 based Genoa-X architecture to the Zen 5 based Turin processors. For the OMP=4 configuration, a single node with 2x96-core Turin platform achieves a runtime of approximately 430s compared to 493s on the 2x96-core Genoa-X system, corresponding to a performance improvement of about 15%. Similar relative gains are observed across larger node counts, indicating that the architectural advantages of Zen 5 are preserved as the simulation scales. This suggests that the performance benefit is not limited to single-node execution but remains effective in distributed-memory configurations where inter-node communication becomes increasingly important. Considering the fact that the underlined platforms offer the same cores count, the gain is likely driven by the higher instructions-per-cycle capability, enhanced memory subsystem, and other optimizations introduced in Zen 5 cores. The results indicate that WRF-SFIRE is able to effectively exploit these improvements despite already benefiting from the larger cache capacity available on Genoa-X.

Among all evaluated systems, the 2x128-core Turin platform delivers the shortest execution times. Compared to a single node with 2x96-core Turin configuration, the runtime decreases from approximately 474s to 409s, corresponding to a performance improvement of about 14%. This advantage is consistently observed across two nodes setup as well, indicating that the application continues to benefit from the additional computational resources provided by the 128-core processors.

However, the transition from the 2x128-core Turin processor to the 2x192-core Turin Dense processor does not provide further performance gains. Despite the significantly higher core count, the Turin Dense platform exhibits slightly longer runtimes. This behaviour suggests that WRF-SFIRE does not fully utilize the additional Zen 5c cores and that the increased degree of parallelism is unable to compensate for architectural trade-offs associated with dense-core designs, including lower cache capacity per core and reduced memory bandwidth available per processing element.

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The Intel Xeon 6980P platform occupies an intermediate position between the AMD Zen 4 and Zen 5 based systems. While it clearly outperforms the baseline Genoa configuration, it remains slower than all evaluated Turin processors. One possible explanation is the significantly higher operating frequency available on the AMD platform. For example, the EPYC 9655 processor used in the 2x96-core Turin configuration operates at a base frequency of 2.6 GHz and can reach boost frequencies of up to 4.1 GHz. In contrast, the Xeon 6980P provides a base frequency of approximately 2.0 GHz with maximum turbo frequencies around 3.2 GHz. Consequently, the AMD processor benefits from roughly 25–30% higher peak clock frequencies.

However, the observed performance differences cannot be attributed to frequency alone. The Intel platform employs a substantially larger L2 cache capacity per core, whereas AMD relies more heavily on a large shared L3 cache organization within CCDs. The results suggest that, for the memory-access patterns characteristic of WRF-SFIRE, the combination of higher operating frequencies, efficient cache hierarchy, and the architectural improvements introduced in Zen 5 provides a more favourable execution environment than the Granite Rapids architecture.

Overall, the comparison indicates that WRF-SFIRE benefits more from strong per-core performance and an efficient memory subsystem than from simply increasing the total number of available cores. This observation is further supported by the fact that all evaluated Turin processors outperform the Xeon 6980P despite the latter providing a larger core count than the 2x96-core Turin configuration.

Figure 16 compares the average power consumption per node measured on the evaluated platforms using the OMP=4 configuration. The Genoa and Genoa-X systems exhibit the lowest average power consumption, while the Turin processors require progressively higher power levels as the number of cores increases.

Figure 16. Average power demand per node measured for AMD-based platforms when using the OMP=4 configuration.

The three 96-core platforms - Genoa, Genoa-X, and Turin - operate on very similar average power consumption levels. As expected, the Genoa-X and Turin processors require slightly more power than the baseline Genoa platform, reflecting the impact of

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the larger cache capacity in Genoa-X and the architectural enhancements introduced in Zen 5. Genoa exhibits the lowest power demand, followed by Genoa-X and the 2x96-core Turin platform, which consume approximately 3-5% and 5-8% more power, respectively. A substantially larger increase is observed for the higher-core-count Turin processors, with both the 2x128-core Turin and 2x192-core Turin Dense systems requiring around 30-40% more power than the 96-core configurations. Despite providing significantly more cores, the Turin Dense processor does not increase power consumption proportionally, highlighting the improved efficiency of the Zen 5c architecture.

Figure 17 presents the total energy consumption achieved on the evaluated platforms. Unlike average power consumption, which is primarily determined by processor architecture and operating frequency, total energy consumption is influenced by both power demand and execution time.

Figure 17. Energy consumption comparison measured for AMD-based platforms when using the OMP=4 configuration.

Despite their higher average power consumption, the Turin processors frequently achieve lower total energy consumption than the Genoa-based systems due to their substantially shorter runtimes. For example, the 2x128-core Turin platform consumes approximately 15-25% less energy than the 2x96-core Genoa system across the evaluated node counts, despite operating at a noticeably higher average power level. This observation demonstrates that minimizing power consumption alone does not necessarily minimize total energy usage. Instead, energy efficiency depends on achieving an appropriate balance between computational throughput and power demand.

Although 96-core Genoa and Genoa-X processors operate within a similar power envelope, the shorter runtime achieved by the Genoa-X platform translates directly into lower energy consumption. Depending on the node count, the energy savings achieved by Genoa-X range from approximately 8% to 15% relative to the standard

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Genoa configuration. Consequently, the larger cache capacity provided by AMD 3D V-Cache improves not only performance but also overall energy efficiency.

Among the evaluated systems, the 2x128-core Turin platform provides one of the most favourable combinations of runtime and energy consumption. Compared with the other AMD-based platforms, it achieves lower total energy consumption while also delivering shorter execution times. In contrast, the 2x192-core Turin Dense processor offers only marginal additional energy savings despite its substantially higher core count, indicating diminishing returns from further increases in processor parallelism for this workload.

Overall, the results demonstrate that both cache capacity and processor microarchitecture significantly influence the performance and energy efficiency of WRF-SFIRE. The transition from Genoa to Genoa-X highlights the benefits of larger cache resources, while the transition from Zen 4 to Zen 5 provides an even larger performance improvement. At the same time, the results indicate that increasing core counts beyond 128 cores per node yields diminishing returns for this workload. The findings suggest that WRF-SFIRE benefits primarily from strong per-core performance, efficient cache utilization, and high memory throughput rather than from maximizing the total number of available cores.

In addition to the processor-level comparison, the scalability of WRF-SFIRE was evaluated using one, two, and four compute nodes. The results demonstrate that increasing the number of nodes consistently reduces the overall runtime across all evaluated platforms. However, the achieved speedup remains sublinear, indicating the growing influence of MPI communication and synchronization overheads as the execution is distributed across a larger number of nodes.

Table 3 summarizes the strong-scaling characteristics obtained for the OMP=4 configuration. The speedup values S_2 and S_4 are defined as the ratio of the execution time achieved on a single node to the execution time obtained on two and four nodes, respectively. The corresponding parallel efficiencies, E_2 and E_4 , are calculated by dividing the achieved speedup by the ideal speedup and are expressed as percentages.

Table 3. Strong-scaling speedup and parallel efficiency obtained for the OMP=4 configuration.

Platform	S_2	S_4	E_2 [%]	E_4 [%]
2x96-core Genoa	1.40	1.89	69.9	47.2
2x96-core Genoa-X	1.51	2.12	75.6	53.0
2x96-core Turin	1.55	1.94	77.3	48.4
2x128-core Turin	1.48	--	74.0	--
2x192-core Turin	1.40	1.21	69.8	30.3

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The results indicate moderate strong-scaling efficiency across all evaluated platforms. While the use of additional compute nodes consistently reduces the overall runtime, the achieved speedups remain significantly below the ideal values, particularly for four-node executions. The highest efficiency is observed on the Genoa-X and Turin platforms, whereas the 2x192-core Turin Dense system exhibits the lowest scalability. This behaviour suggests that the investigated WRF-SFIRE usecase does not provide sufficient computational work per processing element to fully utilize the available parallel resources. As the number of nodes and cores increases, the amount of work assigned to each MPI process decreases, while communication and synchronization overheads become increasingly dominant. Consequently, the overall scalability of WRF-SFIRE appears to be limited primarily by communication costs rather than by processor performance alone.

4.3 Profiling results

In the first stage of the performance profiling process, the memory subsystem is analysed to assess its impact on application performance. The analysis is based on the metrics summarized in Table 4, while the corresponding L3 cache miss rates are illustrated in Figure 18. The table reports the L3 cache miss ratio, the number of L3 cache misses per thousand instructions (L3 Miss PTI), the average latency of L3 cache misses, and the achieved memory bandwidth for the best-performing hybrid configuration employing four OpenMP threads per MPI process. The results are presented for one, two, and four compute nodes in order to investigate the impact of both processor architecture and application scaling on memory-system efficiency.

Figure 18 demonstrates substantial differences in cache utilisation among the investigated AMD processor generations. The Genoa-X platform consistently achieves the lowest L3 cache miss rate, ranging from approximately 30% on a single node to 40% on four nodes. This behaviour can be directly attributed to the additional 3D V-Cache capacity, which significantly increases the amount of data retained within the last-level cache and reduces the frequency of accesses to main memory. In comparison, the standard Genoa processors exhibit miss rates between 46% and 50%, while the Turin-based systems reach values exceeding 60% in the case of the 384-core configuration.

Table 4. Memory subsystem metrics across different node counts for the OMP = 4 configuration.

Platform	L3 Miss [%] (1;2;4 nodes)	L3 Miss Latency [ns] (1;2;4 nodes)	Mem BW [GB/s] (1;2;4 nodes)
2x96-core Genoa	45; 46; 50	183; 172; 154	218; 139; 87
2x96-core Genoa-X	30; 36; 40	154; 145; 131	147; 103; 65
2x96-core Turin	47; 47; 52	244; 234; 201	276; 195; 125

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2x128-core Turin	47; 50; –	310; 268; –	317; 184; –
2x192-core Turin	58; 60; 64	252; 245; 213	334; 234; 120

Figure 18. Comparison of L3 cache miss rates across AMD processor for the OMP=4 setup.

The L3 Miss PTI metric confirms these observations. Genoa-X consistently generates the lowest number of L3 cache misses relative to the executed instruction count, indicating that the larger cache capacity effectively reduces memory pressure. Although Turin processors exhibit comparable or even lower L3 Miss PTI values for some configurations, they simultaneously experience considerably higher miss ratios. This indicates that the application generates a similar amount of memory requests, but a larger fraction of them cannot be satisfied by the available cache resources.

The memory bandwidth results provide additional insight into the observed behaviour. Genoa-X consistently requires the lowest memory bandwidth despite delivering competitive application performance. This observation indicates that the larger cache hierarchy successfully eliminates a significant fraction of memory traffic. Conversely, the Turin processors generate substantially higher memory bandwidth, reaching more than 330 GB/s for the 384-core processor. While this higher bandwidth demand reflects the increased L3 miss rate and more frequent accesses to main memory, it also demonstrates the capability of the Turin platform to efficiently utilize the available memory subsystem and maintain high computational throughput. These observations demonstrate that memory hierarchy characteristics remain one of the key factors influencing the performance of WRF-SFIRE.

In the second stage of the performance profiling process, the computational characteristics and processor execution efficiency are analysed to determine how effectively the available hardware resources are utilized. The analysis is based on the metrics summarized in Table 5 and includes floating-point throughput (FP GFLOPS), SIMD instruction utilization, pipeline efficiency indicators, and instructions per cycle

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(IPC). The presented results correspond to the best-performing hybrid configuration employing four OpenMP threads per MPI process and are reported for one, two, and four compute nodes.

Table 5. Computational and pipeline efficiency metrics for the OMP = 4 configuration.

Platform	FP [GLOPS]	SIMD Utilization 512/256/128/Scalar [%]	Frontend Bound [%]	Backend Bound [%]	IPC
2×96-core Genoa	325	0.44 / 0.04 / 67.6 / 31.9	4.3	58.4	2.06
	250		4.6	54.8	2.25
	171		5.5	50.6	2.44
2×96-core Genoa-X	392	0.45 / 0.04 / 67.3 / 32.2	4.3	54.4	2.28
	312		4.2	54.3	2.31
	226		4.8	52.5	2.36
2×96-core Turin	412	0.28 / 0.02 / 67.7 / 32.0	16.1	53.4	2.29
	346		17.4	49.0	2.54
	244		20	44.9	2.64
2×128-core Turin	496	0.32 / 0.01 / 68.1 / 31.6	16.6	55.2	2.11
	356		17.5	48.1	2.59
2×192-core Turin	456	0.34 / 0.02 / 69.3 / 30.4	16.9	54.9	2.11
	348		18.2	49.1	2.47
	182		19.7	43.6	2.76

The floating-point throughput results reveal substantial differences among the investigated processor generations. The Turin-based systems consistently achieve the highest computational throughput, reaching nearly 500 GFLOPS for the 256-core configuration. In comparison, the Genoa and Genoa-X processors deliver lower floating-point performance despite exhibiting superior cache efficiency, as demonstrated in the previous section.

The SIMD utilization metrics provide additional insight into the computational behaviour of WRF-SFIRE. Across all investigated platforms, the application mainly employs 128-bit floating-point instructions, accounting for approximately 68–70% of all floating-point operations. The utilization of 256-bit instructions remains negligible, while the contribution of AVX-512 instructions is below 1% for all configurations. Furthermore, approximately 30% of floating-point operations are still executed in scalar mode. These results indicate that the application exhibits only limited vectorization and does not significantly benefit from the wide SIMD execution capabilities available in modern processor architectures.

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The pipeline utilization metrics further explain the observed performance differences. The Genoa and Genoa-X processors exhibit relatively low frontend stall rates, typically below 5%, while backend-related stalls account for more than half of all pipeline slots. This behaviour is consistent with the memory subsystem analysis, which identified memory access latency and cache misses as the dominant performance-limiting factors. In contrast, the Turin processors show significantly higher frontend activity but simultaneously achieve lower backend stall rates, particularly for larger node counts. This indicates that the Zen 5 microarchitecture is more effective at hiding memory-access latency and maintaining a higher rate of useful instruction execution.

While Genoa-X benefits from the lowest cache miss rates, the highest IPC values are generally observed on the Turin platforms. In particular, the Turin-384 configuration reaches IPC values approaching 2.8 for the largest scale considered. This demonstrates that the improvements introduced in the Zen 5 architecture allow the processor to sustain higher execution efficiency even in the presence of a less effective cache hierarchy than Genoa X.

Furthermore, the results presented in Table 4 and in Table 5 indicate underlined metrics changes as the number of compute nodes increases. While the L3 cache miss rate generally increases with scale, both memory bandwidth utilization and backend-related pipeline stalls tend to decrease. The results show that the computational characteristics of the workload evolve with increasing node count. Since increasing the number of nodes reduces the size of the local computational domain assigned to each MPI process, the observed changes are likely associated with the growing importance of inter-process communication. A detailed investigation of this effect is provided in the following section based on dedicated MPI communication profiling results.

4.4 MPI analysis

To provide a consistent and unbiased comparison of communication characteristics across processor generations, the MPI profiling analysis is restricted to computing platforms offering an identical core count of 2x96 cores per node. Consequently, the discussion focuses on systems based on the AMD EPYC 9654 (Genoa), AMD EPYC 9684X (Genoa-X), and AMD EPYC 9965 (Turin) processors. This approach eliminates the influence of differing core counts and MPI process configurations, allowing the analysis to focus on architectural effects and communication characteristics that are directly attributable to the processor generation.

As expected, the performed tests reveal that the transferred data volume is identical for the Genoa, Genoa-X and Turin based systems featured the same number of cores. It indicates that the communication requirements are primarily determined by the application decomposition rather than processor microarchitecture. Figure 19 presents the aggregated MPI data transfer volume for the evaluated 2x96-core platforms.

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Figure 19. Aggregated Data Transfer Volume obtained for 1, 2 and 4 nodes setup with 2x96-core CPUs (Genoa, Genoa X, and Turin).

As shown in Figure 19, a noticeable reduction in the total communication volume can be observed with increasing numbers of OpenMP threads per MPI rank. For example, on a single-node configuration, the transferred data volume decreases from approximately 34 TB for the pure MPI configuration (OMP=1) to about 5.4 TB for the most hybrid configuration (OMP=16), corresponding to a reduction of more than six times. Similar trends are observed for two-node and four-node executions.

The reduction in communication volume is directly associated with the decreasing number of MPI processes participating in the simulation. As the number of OpenMP threads per rank increases, fewer computational subdomains are created, resulting in fewer communication interfaces and, consequently, a lower volume of exchanged halo data. Therefore, the observed behaviour is primarily governed by the domain decomposition strategy of WRF-SFIRE and the number of MPI processes employed rather than by architectural differences between processors.

Furthermore, the total communication volume increases with the number of compute nodes. For the OMP=4 configuration, previously identified as providing the best performance-energy trade-off, the transferred volume grows from approximately 13.5 TB on a single node to about 35.4 TB on four nodes. Compared with the pure MPI configuration (OMP=1), this represents a reduction of approximately 60% in communication volume while preserving the most favourable overall execution characteristics. The increase in transferred volume with node count reflects the growing communication surface between computational subdomains as the domain is partitioned among a larger number of MPI ranks distributed across multiple nodes.

Figure 20 presents the average communication cost per MPI rank, separated into point-to-point (P2P) and collective communication components. The metric represents the communication overhead experienced by an individual MPI process presenting a direct comparison across different MPI/OpenMP configurations and processor generations.

Single-node results provide a suitable environment for evaluating the impact of processor architecture on communication-related overheads, as all communication

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remains within a single compute node and is unaffected by the InfiniBand interconnect. Across all investigated MPI/OpenMP setups for the single-node results (Figure 20 a-c), the Turin platform consistently achieves the lowest communication cost per rank, followed by Genoa-X and Genoa CPUs. This trend indicates that successive processor generations improve the efficiency of MPI costs, reducing the communication overhead even though the overall communication pattern of the application remains unchanged (see Figure 19). In particular, the large L3 cache available in Genoa-X and the architectural enhancements introduced with Turin not only accelerate the computational phase of the application but also help mitigate MPI overheads by improving data locality and reducing the cost of communication and synchronization between ranks.

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Figure 20. Average MPI communication cost per rank for different MPI/OpenMP configurations.

As shown in Figure 20, we observe a consistent reduction in communication cost per rank as the number of OpenMP threads per MPI rank increases from 1 to 8. This trend is primarily associated with the decreasing number of MPI processes and the corresponding reduction in communication interfaces between neighbouring computational subdomains. As a result, each rank experiences lower communication overhead and synchronization costs. However, the communication cost reaches its minimum for configurations employing 4–8 OpenMP threads per MPI rank. For the OMP=16 configuration, a negligible increase in communication cost is observed on all investigated platforms, suggesting that the benefits of further MPI rank reduction are

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partially offset by additional thread-level overheads. This observation is consistent with the performance results presented in the previous section, where the best performance–energy trade-off was also achieved for 4–8 OpenMP threads per rank.

Figure 21. Distribution of MPI communication time among the major communication categories for different MPI/OpenMP configurations.

Furthermore, Figure 20 demonstrates two communication trends across the investigated MPI/OpenMP configurations. The collective communication cost per rank remains comparatively stable, exhibiting only a modest decrease when transitioning from the pure MPI configuration to hybrid execution. In contrast, the point-to-point

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communication cost shows decreases substantially with an increasing number of OpenMP threads per MPI rank. These results outline that the communication-related performance gains associated with hybrid parallelisation are primarily attributable to the reduction of point-to-point communication overhead rather than to changes in the efficiency of collective operations. The observed behaviour can be explained by the decreasing number of MPI ranks in hybrid configurations, which reduces the number of subdomain interfaces and consequently lowers the volume of halo data exchanged between neighbouring processes. As a result, the cost of neighbour-to-neighbour communication is reduced.

The trends observed in Figure 20 are further illustrated in Figure 21, which presents the relative contribution of the individual communication categories to the total MPI communication cost. Figure 21 illustrates how the communication structure evolves with increasing OpenMP parallelism. The results show that the reduction in overall communication cost is accompanied by a decreasing contribution of point-to-point communication, whereas the relative contribution of collective communication becomes increasingly dominant despite its comparatively stable absolute cost. Consequently, the communication profile shifts from being dominated by neighbour-to-neighbour exchanges towards a larger relative contribution of collective operations.

Figure 22 presents the example for communication intensity between neighbouring MPI subdomains for an 8x8 domain decomposition achieved on 2 computing nodes of 2x128-core Turin platform, including the horizontal (left–right) communication pattern and vertical (top–bottom) communication pattern. In both cases, a highly regular communication structure can be observed, indicating a well-balanced decomposition of the computational domain and a uniform distribution of communication workload among MPI ranks.

Figure 22. Communication intensity of WRF-SFIRE for 8x8 MPI decomposition.

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We observe that the exchanged communication volume is slightly higher for vertical neighbour interactions. While horizontal exchanges typically involve approximately 15-16 GB of data, vertical communications reach approximately 18-19 GB. The size of the exchanged halo regions is slightly larger in the vertical direction, resulting in increased communication requirements between top-bottom neighbouring subdomains. Nevertheless, the communication remains highly structured and balanced across the entire MPI decomposition. The highly regular and symmetric communication structure is also a consequence of the square 8x8 domain decomposition, where each MPI rank has a similar neighbourhood configuration and communication responsibilities. Consequently, the communication remains well balanced across the entire MPI decomposition, confirming that the observed behaviour is largely determined by the geometric properties of the decomposition and the stencil-based halo exchange mechanism employed by WRF-SFIRE.

In contrast, the communication maps obtained for the 4x8 domain decomposition (Figure 23) exhibit a noticeably stronger directional asymmetry. While the horizontal neighbour exchanges remain at approximately 15-16 GB, the communication volume associated with vertical interactions increases to approximately 34-35 GB, more than twice the horizontal communication volume. This behaviour differs from the 8x8 decomposition, where the communication volumes in both directions are approximately equal (16 GB and 18–19 GB for horizontal and vertical communication, respectively). The observed increase stems from the elongated shape of the computational subdomains in the 4x8 decomposition, which enlarges the communication interfaces in the vertical direction and consequently increases the amount of halo data exchanged. Future work will investigate how different domain decomposition strategies influence the overall execution time and parallel efficiency of WRF-SFIRE, and whether communication-aware decompositions can further improve application scalability.

Figure 23. Communication intensity of WRF-SFIRE for 4x8 MPI decomposition.

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5 Performance analysis of sparse LLM inference

This section evaluates the performance, scalability, and parallel scheduling of sparse transformer architectures on modern CPU-based HPC systems to optimize resource efficiency for environmental and operational workloads. The results of this work have also been published at the HPAI4S Workshop of the IEEE International Parallel & Distributed Processing Symposium conference in Milan [7].

5.1 Large Language Model Applications in environmental computing and HPC infrastructure

While the core mission of the HiDALGO2 project focuses on solving large-scale environmental challenges, dedicating resources to understand LLM performance is a highly strategic investment. LLMs are rapidly moving beyond basic text generation and are becoming vital tools in complex environmental sciences. For example, in wildfire research, LLM-based multi-agent systems are being benchmarked to coordinate emergency responses across large maps [8], while generative AI frameworks are replacing traditional physics-based models to predict 2D and 3D fire spread in real-time [9]. In urban air quality management, LLMs are being used to simulate pollutant dispersion as a more efficient alternative to traditional heavy simulation methods [10], and are being adapted to accurately forecast regional air pollution levels even in environments with limited monitoring data [11]. Beyond driving these scientific simulations, LLMs are heavily optimizing how we interact with supercomputers themselves. A prime example is the MareNostrum supercomputer, which deploys terminal-based LLM chatbots to assist researchers with job scheduling, environment setups, and system troubleshooting.

5.2 Background

5.2.1 Self-attention bottlenecks and model sparsification

Large language models (LLMs) have significantly increased in size, leading to intensive computational and memory demands during inference. While the training phase is largely GPU-bound, inference workloads—particularly when exploiting sparsity—can be highly optimized for high-performance computing (HPC) systems using CPUs, offering a highly efficient and energy-aware alternative. Their core transformer architecture [12] relies heavily on dense matrix multiplications, but introducing sparsity [13] into the activations and weights can drastically reduce both memory overhead and computational costs. (see Figure 24) Through sparsification, standard dense kernels are replaced by Sparse Matrix-Matrix Multiplication (SpMM) and Sampled Dense-Dense Matrix Multiplication (SDDMM). Previous research has primarily focused on optimizing these SpMM and SDDMM operations in isolation. However, evaluating them exclusively at the individual kernel level overlooks critical

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opportunities for parallel execution and scheduling optimizations across the complete transformer pipeline, which could significantly enhance cache utilization and overall system efficiency.

Figure 24. Comparison of execution time between Dense-Dense (MKL_GEMM) and Sparse-Dense (MKL_CSR) matrix multiplication.

5.2.2 Sparse multi-head attention pipeline

The multi-head attention mechanism processes tokenized input sequences through a specific pipeline (Figure 25):

Figure 25. The attention pipeline for one sparse head of the transformer block.

- **QKV Calculation:** The input token embeddings are multiplied by the QKV weights to generate three distinct vectors: Query (Q), Key (K), and Value (V). By sparsifying the model weights, these three multiplications function as SpMM operations.
- **Masked Self-Attention:** To determine the similarity between query-key pairs, the Q and K matrices are multiplied alongside a lower triangular mask to produce an attention score. By applying a sparsified mask, this computation is handled by the SDDMM kernel to eliminate unnecessary internal multiplications. A softmax function is subsequently applied to convert these masked scores into attention weights.

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- Output: The layer's final output is computed by multiplying the attention weights with the Value (V) matrix, which constitutes another SpMM operation.

Rather than computing a single representation, the transformer utilizes multiple independent attention heads to focus on different elements of the input sequence. These individual head outputs are then concatenated and linearly transformed.

SpMM computations most commonly utilize the Compressed Sparse Row (CSR) format, which strictly stores non-zero values alongside their column indices and row pointers, ensuring calculations focus solely on non-zero elements to decrease memory bandwidth requirements. SDDMM computes the product of two dense matrices but uses a predefined mask to sample only a specific subset of the output elements, making its performance highly dependent on the mask's specific sparsity pattern.

5.3 Experimental results

A comprehensive evaluation was conducted to benchmark the performance and scalability of sparse kernels both individually and within the complete transformer pipeline.

5.3.1 Hardware setup

Testing was executed on a 64-core AMD EPYC 7H12 CPU equipped with 256 MB of Last Level Cache, located on the Discoverer Supercomputer [14]. Computations were restricted to the 64 cores of a single socket to isolate performance and prevent Non-Uniform Memory Access (NUMA) effects.

5.3.2 Benchmark configuration

For SpMM execution, we utilized the Intel MKL CSR implementation (MKL_CSR) [15]. In contrast, the SDDMM kernel is executed using the TACO library [16], as Intel MKL does not natively support this operation. Thread pinning to specific processor cores was managed via OpenMP environment variables, and matrices were initialized in parallel utilizing a Linux first-touch policy. To accurately simulate continuous inference workloads, the CPU cache was primed with 100 warm-up iterations prior to capturing performance metrics on a single, subsequent iteration. Concurrent pipeline implementations leveraged OpenMP tasks to invoke the SpMM kernels simultaneously.

5.3.3 Dataset

The evaluation leveraged sparse transformer matrices from the Deep Learning Matrix Collection (DLMC) [17], [18]. To maintain consistency, a sequence length of 512 tokens was used across all experiments, perfectly aligning with the 512x512 dimensions of the DLMC weight matrices.

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5.3.4 SpMM and SDDMM scalability and performance

Analyzing the kernels individually revealed distinct behavioural traits (Figure 26):

- The SpMM kernel demonstrates near-linear scalability up to 32 threads. On a 64-core system, 16 threads proved to be the optimal configuration for running multiple SpMM kernels concurrently. However, scalability begins to drop at higher thread counts (32 and 64). This drop is especially noticeable at higher sparsity levels.

Figure 26. SpMM and SDDMM different sparsity ratios and varying numbers of threads.

- Following the same methodology as delivered in [17], for the SDDMM kernel we used a randomly generated 95% sparse lower triangular mask with a small dense band. Compared to SpMM, the SDDMM kernel actually exhibits superior scalability. Despite this, its raw throughput is substantially lower. This is because the TACO implementation relies on a basic OpenMP parallel loop instead of a highly optimized vendor library. To manage this performance gap, SDDMM is executed independently. By assigning it all 64 threads, it prevents the slower kernel from becoming a bottleneck for the broader pipeline.

5.3.5 Serial pipeline exploration

A baseline sequential pipeline was tested, allocating the full CPU (64 threads) to each operation consecutively (Figure 27). At sparsity levels below 90%, the generation of the Q, K, and V matrices dominates the overall pipeline execution time. However, at higher sparsities, the SDDMM and the final SpMM output kernels become the most computationally intensive. The final SpMM kernel specifically experiences degraded performance due to higher cache miss ratios; earlier kernels benefit from cache pre-warming generated by the immediate processing of input embeddings.

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Figure 27. A breakdown of the total execution time of a serialized transformer.

Overall, the strictly serial pipeline mirrors the scalability of the SpMM kernel (Figure 28), scaling effectively only up to 16 threads and yielding diminishing returns beyond that threshold.

Figure 28. Performance of the total serial transformer pipeline.

5.3.6 Theoretical concurrent pipeline exploration

To maximize CPU utilization, a theoretical parallel schedule was constructed based on empirical scalability data. In this model, the Q, K, and V SpMM kernels execute simultaneously, allocated 16 threads each. The pipeline then reverts to sequential execution across all 64 threads for the SDDMM and final SpMM kernels. An alternative model running just the K and Q kernels concurrently on 32 threads each resulted in inferior performance. (Figure 29).

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Figure 29. Theoretical performance comparison of serial(left) vs. parallel(right) transformer pipeline.

The 3x16 concurrent strategy theoretically yields an average 20% reduction in total execution time across all sparsity levels, a significant improvement considering 16 CPU threads (a quarter of the processor) remain completely unutilized during the concurrent phase.

5.3.7 Empirical bottlenecks

Attempting to empirically execute the concurrent 3x16 schedule exposed severe performance degradation in the MKL_CSR kernels due to several system-level bottlenecks:

- **Scheduling Overhead:** Managing OpenMP tasks requires dedicating distinct threads purely for scheduling overhead, reducing the pool of threads available for mathematical computation. This prevents configurations like running four 16-thread tasks concurrently on a 64-core machine.
- **NUMA and Partitioning Constraints:** The Intel MKL implementation experiences performance drops when allocated thread counts are not multiples of eight, likely stemming from the CPU architecture where the L3 cache is shared amongst groups of eight cores.
- **Affinity and Load Balancing:** MKL threads actively resist manual thread binding. Executing without thread affinity causes performance to drop below single-threaded levels. Even when strictly setting OpenMP variables (OMP_PLACES, OMP_PROC_BIND) for nested parallelism, the SpMM kernels operate at only 50% efficiency, indicating thread overlap and contention across core groups.
- **Static Affinities:** OpenMP environment variables dictating thread affinity are static and locked at runtime. Consequently, the downstream SDDMM and final SpMM kernels—which run sequentially and could utilize the full CPU—cannot dynamically adopt optimal affinity settings, leading to poor late-pipeline performance.

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5.4 Conclusions and Future Work

While optimizing SpMM and SDDMM as isolated operations is critical for LLM inference, treating the transformer head as a strictly serial pipeline overlooks substantial opportunities. Concurrently scheduling independent matrix operations—such as executing three SpMM kernels in parallel with 16 threads each—demonstrates clear theoretical potential to improve resource utilization and reduce execution times. However, empirical implementation is currently hindered by resource contention, suboptimal thread affinity adherence within vendor libraries, and static partitioning constraints.

Future work will seek to bypass these limitations by leveraging compiler-specific instructions (e.g., `KMP_AFFINITY`) for fine-grained thread control and developing custom, pipeline-aware SpMM kernels. Additionally, optimizing the SDDMM implementation to match SpMM speeds could allow it to run concurrently with the final output step. Lastly, further experiments should be conducted on Intel-based architectures to better leverage the MKL library's native optimizations, while also exploring MPI as an alternative to OpenMP for the concurrent scheduling of the kernels.

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6 Conclusions

The D3.6 deliverable focuses on evaluating emerging trends in HPC processor architectures through the analysis of state-of-the-art server platforms. Particular attention is devoted to the latest AMD EPYC 9005 series processors and their comparison with the previous-generation AMD EPYC 9004 family investigated in Deliverables D3.4 [2] and D3.5 [1]. In addition, the study includes a comparison with the Intel Xeon 6980P processor to provide a broader perspective on current HPC CPU architectures.

The evaluation is based on the Wildfires use case implemented using the WRF-SFIRE model, a coupled fire–atmosphere simulation framework that combines the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model with the SFIRE wildfire spread and fuel-moisture components. The benchmark focuses on the MPI+OpenMP implementation of WRF-SFIRE, enabling the assessment of how modern processor features, including larger cache capacities, DDR5 memory technology, and increasing core counts, affect application performance and energy efficiency.

The conducted benchmarking demonstrates that WRF-SFIRE performance is strongly influenced by both processor microarchitecture and the selected hybrid MPI+OpenMP configuration. Across all evaluated platforms, hybrid execution consistently outperformed the pure MPI configuration, with the OMP=4 setup providing the best balance between runtime, power consumption, and overall energy efficiency.

Among the investigated systems, the AMD EPYC Turin processors based on the Zen 5 architecture achieved the highest performance, while the AMD EPYC Genoa-X platform confirmed the benefits of 3D V-Cache technology for this workload. The Intel Xeon 6980P delivered competitive results but remained slower than the evaluated Turin configurations. Overall, the results indicate that WRF-SFIRE benefits primarily from strong per-core performance, efficient cache utilization, and a high-performance memory subsystem.

Although the Turin processors exhibited higher average power consumption than the Genoa-based systems, their shorter execution times resulted in lower total energy consumption. Consequently, the 2×128-core Turin platform emerged as the most attractive compromise between performance and energy efficiency among the evaluated processor architectures.

In addition to the performance and energy evaluation, the current study extends the analysis with detailed hardware profiling and MPI communication characterization. Hardware-level profiling was performed using AMD µProf to investigate cache utilization, memory-system behaviour, SIMD efficiency, floating-point activity, and processor pipeline utilization across the evaluated AMD EPYC platforms. Furthermore, MPI profiling was conducted to analyse communication patterns, quantify point-to-point and collective communication overheads, and assess the impact of domain decomposition and hybrid MPI+OpenMP configurations on application scalability.

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In addition to traditional HPC benchmarking activities, the project also addresses the rapidly growing field of Large Language Models (LLMs), which have become an important component of modern HPC and AI-driven computing ecosystems. Beyond their widespread use in natural language processing, LLMs are increasingly being integrated into scientific computing workflows, environmental modelling, and supercomputing infrastructures. Within HiDALGO2, this activity focuses on understanding the performance characteristics of sparse transformer architectures on modern HPC systems, with particular emphasis on scalability, resource efficiency, and energy-aware execution. These investigations complement the project's core environmental applications and provide valuable insights into the role of AI-driven workloads in current and future HPC ecosystems.

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